

Data Monetization Opportunities and Challenges: The European Landscape by DATAMITE^{*}

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Abstract. In Europe, data monetization presents a promising goal for new revenue streams exploiting the power of the data. Nevertheless, obstacles such as regulatory environment and internal organizational constraints create a skepticism. DATAMITE project addresses these challenges and proposes a holistic framework designed to streamline the data monetization journey. Offering modules centered on data governance, quality assurance, and security, DATAMITE equips stakeholders with the tools necessary to optimize the value of their data. By ensuring trust and fostering collaboration, DATAMITE assures the expansion and competitiveness of European industries in data market. Through its comprehensive approach, DATAMITE aims to unlock opportunities and guide European enterprises towards success in the dynamic landscape of the digital economy.

Keywords: DATAMITE · Monetization · data economy.

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1 Introduction

In the digital age, data plays a crucial role in strategic decision-making, yet the true value and Return on Investment (ROI) of data and analytics (D&A) products can be uncertain. Businesses must adapt to changing consumer expectations for highly personalized experiences. Data monetization emerges as a strategic avenue to meet these demands, fostering customer satisfaction and loyalty, and giving companies a competitive edge in the market [27].

Over the past year, amidst the challenges posed by highly publicized generative AI and ongoing uncertainty, D&A leaders have made significant strides in fostering trust and enabling enterprises to become truly data driven. Key innovations in data governance, data literacy, modern business intelligence, and analytics, as well as advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and techniques like data fabric and data monetization, have played pivotal roles in this endeavor. As organizations recognize data as an asset, the concept of monetizing data has emerged as a common goal. Many businesses are transitioning into information-driven entities, acknowledging the increasing volume and importance of the data they generate and consume. While it has become somewhat cliché to assert that data is the most valuable asset of an enterprise, the underlying truth remains undeniable: the data an organization meticulously collects, cleanses, and stores holds immense monetary value. Consequently, organizations are increasingly exploring avenues to unlock additional revenue streams from external parties by leveraging their data assets.

DATAMITE, an EU funded project aims to address the benefits but also the challenges of data monetization for European organizations and propose strategies to be adopted by offering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve data monetizing, interoperability, trading and exchange, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

The DATAMITE project addresses barriers hindering European enterprises and public administrations in capitalizing on their data. Through a technical framework, DATAMITE streamlines the monetization process, aiming to maximize data value, governance, and trustworthiness. Essential modules include Data Governance, Quality Assurance, Security Measures, and Sharing & Support Tools, emphasizing interoperability and open-source components.

Internally, DATAMITE enhances data quality management and adherence to FAIR principles, fostering trust and closing the data-decision gap. Externally, it opens new revenue streams and collaboration opportunities, supporting participation in ecosystems like International Data Spaces (IDS), data markets, and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Additionally, DATAMITE aids Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in educating Small Medium Enterprises (SME) and low-tech companies on integrating into the data economy.

The benefits and opportunities that arise from data monetization are expected to be numerous and have a high impact on the revenue and the competitiveness of companies across all industries. But various risks must also be considered. In the following sections, the opportunities but also the challenges

that arise from data monetization will be presented, accompanied by several industry use cases.

This document explores Data Monetization through the perspective of DATAMITE. It presents data as an asset and gives a motivation for European organizations to share their data. In Section 2, describes use cases in various sectors, while in Section 3 presents the opportunities and the challenges that organizations face or might face when monetizing their data. Next, Section 4 concludes by summarizing key points and future possibilities for data monetization in Europe.

1.1 Data as an asset

Data has been used as part of the business in the rapidly evolving digitalization of the industrial ecosystem. Several innovation segments – e.g. retail, finance, marketing and communications, healthcare – made data an asset and use used them as key pillar of their business strategy. Therefore, huge efforts have been taken to harvest and analyze data in order to propel industry. These processes are string along with the analysis of the logic and practice of data monetization as an asset, including personal corporate data [2].

The core challenge behind the data innovation strategy encompasses the part of the pipeline associated with the harvest of data to be fed into analytics. There is an extended belief that the collection of large amounts of data favour decision-making processes and therefore, at the end of the business process the actions must pose economic benefits for the data owner. However, the exploitation of digital data is not trivial. It requires a holistic approach, from technical to organisation capabilities, to execute a successful innovation data lifecycle.

Literature proposes methodssupporting digital processes for mass collection. Some of the data have inherent capabilities to be exploited but are subject to high risks in the processes like, for example, personal or healthcare data. Thus, the collection, use and exploitation of these fields requires awareness of challenges and demands novel technical objectives and structures to minimize risks on the consumption of data. Foremost among the risks are breaking current legislation with personal data (e.g. GDPR) or reducing bias in the consumption of the data by artificial intelligence algorithms. By contrast, the benefits from an exploitation point are quite high on services that pursue a better understanding of the impact of products, predictions, or decision-making tools.

In terms of value for data, there are different approaches depending on the stakeholder focus. While scientists tend to focus more on the value chain only when certain technological and organizational conditions are satisfied, large companies bootstrap these processes after commercializing them. Google’s chief economist Hal Varian noted that only after selling the data -licensing it in the case of personal data- can the company identify and measure these assets accordingly [34].

Data is clearly introduced as a key asset for many companies along with processes for data production, maintenance, circulation, analytics and reuse. The transformation or adaptation of business processes and resources towards creating an asset and exploitation of data is a fact, and strategic efforts on data

and through data lead towards increasing the portfolio of the core business of many companies. Although data has been always perceived as an organizational resource, the focus on the literature is on the cost of organizing (data as a medium) as opposed to the collection and processing (data as a resource).

1.2 Data Monetization

The concept of data monetization is well established in theory, yet the concrete economic benefits, how organizations quantify the economic impact and the way to get started, often remain unclear to a substantial number of companies. Yet, in this era of digital transformation, many enterprises have placed their trust in becoming data-driven, and one of the reasons (though not the only one) is data monetization and its potential for strategic gains.

According to Gartner, *Data monetization is the practice of extracting monetary value from data, analytics and AI, quantified directly or indirectly in economic or financial terms*. In other terms, Data monetization is using your data to obtain economic benefits. However, it encompasses more than just generating monetary revenues from selling or sharing data with third parties (external), it also involves creating new value, cost saving, improvements and better making decisions (internal).

Direct / Indirect Monetization Two primary approaches to monetizing data are discussed: direct and indirect.

Direct data monetization involves selling data as a product or service, treating data as an asset exchangeable for monetary gain [39]. This can include selling raw data or packaging information products with core offerings, such as through bartering or wrapping practices [36].

Indirect data monetization focuses on using data to enhance existing products, services, or operations, leading to increased revenue through improved offerings or business processes [4, 37]. This can involve providing personalized recommendations, targeted advertisements, or identifying innovative products through research and development [4].

The choice between these approaches depends on factors such as the type of data, competitive landscape, and strategic goals of the business [27]. Combining both approaches can maximize the value of data assets [32, 37].

1.3 Motivation

Monetizing data is increasingly crucial, with data being one of the world's most valuable resources [1, 36]. The global data monetization market was valued at \$2.60 billion in 2022, projected to reach \$9.10 billion by 2030 [11]. Several factors drive this expansion, including the growing volume of generated data, increased awareness of data monetization, and emerging technology opportunities [1, 22]. Technologies such as business intelligence, cloud computing, and Internet of Things (IoT) further contribute to this trend [27].

Monetizing data unlocks hidden value within organizations, serving as an additional income stream and offering customized insights to clients. It also mitigates risks and saves costs for businesses while providing scalability. However, a successful data monetization strategy requires a deep understanding of the organization's unique use case and value proposition [27]. Building on compliance and security foundations is crucial, along with offering flexible data products and building long-term partnerships with clients. To craft such a strategy, the following sections delve into theoretical approaches, revenue models, offerings, and customer segments, drawing from literature and pilot studies.

2 Use Cases in Various Verticals

In our data-driven world, organizations are increasingly turning to data platforms to harness the potential of their data assets. Data platforms serve as the foundation for collecting, storing, processing, and analysing data, enabling a wide range of critical use cases across various industries. This section explores some of the key use cases for data platforms, highlighting their versatility and impact.

2.1 Telecommunications

The telecommunications sector in Europe is experiencing rapid growth in data monetization, projected to reach \$10.1 billion by 2027 with a 22% annual growth rate. Cloud solutions, analytics, and machine learning are driving this surge by optimizing operations, enhancing customer service, and enabling digitalization in Europe. Telcos are exploring direct data sales and data marketplaces, capitalizing on the wealth of customer behavior, device, and location data they possess. While this data unlocks network optimization, personalized experiences, and innovative services, challenges such as strict data protection regulations, cybersecurity risks, legacy systems, limited data expertise, and privacy persist. To navigate these hurdles and unlock the full potential, telecom companies must prioritize compliance, cybersecurity investments, infrastructure upgrades, workforce training, and addressing customer privacy concerns.

2.2 Energy

Data monetization in the European energy sector can revolutionize energy production, distribution, and consumption by leveraging data from smart meters, sensors, and IoT devices. This enables energy companies to optimize production processes, predict demand patterns, and enhance grid operations, leading to improved efficiency and sustainability. Consumers benefit from data analytics by making informed energy consumption decisions, while the integration of renewable energy sources into the grid is facilitated, bolstering grid resilience and reliability through proactive maintenance and outage management. Despite

these benefits, significant barriers such as regulatory complexities, interoperability issues, resistance to change, and high initial costs hinder progress. Overcoming these challenges requires regulatory alignment, technological investments, cultural shifts towards data-driven practices, and collaboration among stakeholders, ultimately unlocking the full potential of data monetization and driving sustainability, efficiency, and resilience in the European energy sector.

2.3 Healthcare (Pharmaceutical)

The healthcare industry is expected to sharply increase the use of raw data soon. Since we live around digitalization of healthcare systems and there is a significant abundance of data being generated, healthcare organizations have already recognized the immense value of their data assets [35]. Specifically for Europe, Data Monetization Market is expected to experience significant growth with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 17.7% during the forecast period of 2023-2030. Healthcare organizations have the opportunity to monetize their data by sharing access to their clinical data with pharmaceutical companies [18].

Healthcare data monetization offers numerous advantages, including revenue generation, data-driven decision-making, research acceleration, improved healthcare delivery, cost optimization, collaborative opportunities, enhanced patient outcomes, and strengthened data governance. These benefits contribute to the holistic growth of the healthcare industry. However, addressing concerns such as data privacy, security, and regulatory compliance is essential to build trust and ensure ethical data practices in this evolving landscape [14].

Pharmaceutical companies can benefit significantly from healthcare data monetization, as it allows them to use the data that they collect throughout their drug development process to generate revenue. Due to the competition in the pharmaceutical industry, companies need to invest in research and product development to create competitive advantage on the market and create new drugs and treatments [30].

2.4 Agriculture

Data monetization in agriculture refers to generating revenue from the agricultural data, basing on the vast amount of information produced by precision agriculture, IoT sensors, satellite imagery, etc. There are different opportunities and strategies to monetize the data: Farm management systems directly integrates data from multiply sources providing decision support systems and predictive analytics (different source of data and machine learning algorithms to forecast crop yields, assess agricultural risk), that are usually fee based. Agri Data marketplaces serve as platforms for buying and selling agricultural data. Data marketplaces allows to charge fees or commissions for facilitating transactions on their platforms. Supply chain technologies are integrating the data from different sources and running on top analytics to optimize the logistics and inventory management. It helps identify opportunities to reduce costs and

increase profitability throughout the supply chain. Data monetization in agriculture have great potential for increasing profitability across the entire food value chain. However, it raises concerns about data privacy, and ownership, which must be addressed to foster trust and ensure compensation for data actors [10].

2.5 Automotive Industry

Vehicle-generated data is increasing exponentially. The Europe automotive data monetization market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 34.62% over the forecasting period of 2023 to 2030 [15]. A big barrier to Data Monetization is the data privacy concerns and the regulation requirements. To ensure fair competition and protect user rights, the EU Data Act has been introduced. This legislation grants users ownership and control over their data, while imposing obligations on automotive Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) to ensure transparency and fairness in data monetization [16]. By 2025, approximately 470 million connected vehicles worldwide are anticipated to generate around 25 gigabytes of data per hour each. Vehicles now offer more than just mechanical features; their value also lies in connectivity and electronic capabilities. They can capture and share various data types such as geolocation, vehicle performance, driver behavior, and biometrics.

Data monetization presents a new frontier for the automotive industry, offering significant benefits. Opportunities include generating revenue through direct monetization and tailored advertising, reducing R&D and material costs, analyzing usage patterns to cut customer costs, enhancing customer satisfaction through personalized products or services, and improving safety and security by collecting real-time warnings for faster intervention. However, many manufacturers lack the necessary IT infrastructure, skills, and capacities to leverage data effectively. Overcoming these challenges requires investment in human resources and systems, potentially increasing budgets, to transform this barrier into a competitive advantage [24].

2.6 Retail

Data monetization in retail offers various advantages. Leveraging customer data can enhance marketing strategies, personalize experiences, and optimize pricing, leading to increased revenue [25]. Retailers can also reduce costs by analyzing inventory and operations. Data analytics enables better decision-making, informs strategic planning, and drives innovation, fostering competitive advantage [39].

However, challenges exist. Retailers often lack clear data monetization strategies, struggle with data privacy regulations, and face organizational barriers like resistance to change and a lack of analytics expertise [25]. Addressing these barriers is crucial for successful data monetization in retail.

3 Opportunities and Challenges

3.1 Opportunities

Existing business models When looking at options for business models of data monetization we first differentiate between different forms of packaging the data and different monetization models:

The packaging refers to the process of preparing and presenting data sets for the use of the buyer or consumer. The simplest way is to sell raw data sets to businesses, researchers, or individuals. This is typically downloadable data with diverse backgrounds as e.g. company addresses with certain selection criteria or spoken language audio recordings for training of a speech recognition system. One step up is to package data as a service. Here, customers can get access on demand e.g. through an API or web interfaces. A typical example would be weather observation data from (national) agencies that are presented in GRIB (GRIdded Binary) files. These can be used by weather apps for further addition of value and further processing like visualisation and forecasting. Such a final offering is then a data product which refers to the output of utilizing data to create a service or an application that provides immediate value to users. There exist also complementary data products that enhance or supplement existing data products, e.g. a data enrichment service that augments an existing data product with additional demographic data to provide deeper context.

The different forms of packaged data can be monetized in different forms. Data licensing where users typically pay a one-time fee or a recurring fee for a defined period during which existing data can be used. The data provider grants in return usage under agreed terms and conditions. In a data subscription model, users pay a recurring fee for ongoing access to data over time. A special case would be pay per data use where the user is paying a one-time fee for a single use. More commonly, single data sets can be bought for a specific price tag and then can be used for an unlimited time (price tag per data set). Another common model is a data partnership, where two institutions or individuals share their data with each other in a barter agreement without money transfer involved.

Access to Markets Data monetization presents diverse business opportunities for companies. Firstly, they can monetize their data by selling it to external organizations, including customer behavior data, market trends, and valuable insights. Analyzing this data enables targeted advertisements and personalized experiences, enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty. Furthermore, data monetization fosters strategic partnerships and collaborations, as sharing insights can drive innovation, improve decision-making, and unlock new revenue streams between companies [13]. The emergence of technologies such as Business Intelligence and Analytics (BI&A), cloud computing, blockchain, IoT, and social networks presents further opportunities for data monetization increasing magnitude of generated data. Furthermore, companies that are Business-to-Business (B2B) driven are also experiencing a rapid increase in the creation and capture of value from data [25]. While data-driven businesses are commonly associated with

the Business-to-Consumer (B2C) sector, the B2B space is also recognizing the potential of data monetization [29]. Despite being in its nascent stage, companies capitalizing on data monetization are gaining competitive advantages. Proactive exploration and utilization of data monetization avenues enable businesses to lead in their industries, capitalizing on its potential for sustained growth and performance [17].

Beyond direct monetization Hopes for data sharing benefits are high, in terms of monetization and beyond. Businesses emphasize all different kinds of potential benefits, which vary considerably between sectors (see examples below). Accordingly, the emphasis of benefits beyond monetization varies, from emphasizing indirect monetization benefits such as product performance and improved customer services to wider societal impacts like improvement in the mobility sector or advancement of scientific research. Examples of sectors that hope for benefits beyond monetization are for example healthcare, the automotive sector, retail, as well as energy and telecommunication, two sectors crucial in the DATAMITE project.

In healthcare, data sharing focuses on accelerating scientific progress while enhancing research quality. In so doing, data sharing here sets out to contribute. On the one hand, sharing data promotes transparency in research, allowing others to verify and reproduce findings (e.g. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable - FAIR principles). This enhances public accountability and strengthens the integrity of the research process. On the other hand, data sharing enables researchers to access a broader range of data. The hopes are that researchers can collaborate more effectively, pool resources, and work together on large-scale projects to increase research output and to generate new knowledge. Besides, data sharing is supposed to prevent duplication of efforts. Building their efforts on existing data sets, given their accuracy and quality suffices, researchers can avoid unnecessary repetition, optimizing the use of resources and maximizing the impact of research efforts [38]. However, the specificity of data (generation) and the use of models must be considered when transferring data between entities, regarding potential bias.

In the automotive industry, the specific benefits of data sharing may vary depending on the context and implementation. Shared data can help improve the performance of vehicles and enhance the overall driving experience. By analyzing large sets of data, automotive manufacturers can gain insights into vehicle performance, identify areas of improvement, and optimize design and functionality [21]. In terms of customer service, sharing data with stakeholders, such as repair shops and service providers, can improve communication and enhance the efficiency of repair and maintenance processes. This may lead to faster and more accurate diagnostics, streamlined servicing, and improved customer satisfaction [23]. In context of mobility more generally, data sharing is hoped to improve road safety, traffic situations and to reduce fuel consumption. By collecting and analyzing data from various vehicles, traffic patterns and congestion can be better

understood, leading to more efficient traffic management and reduced congestion [3]. Yet, whether these wider benefits will occur still needs to be proven.

In the retail industry, data sharing is expected to facilitate real-time collaboration among teams and departments to improve teamwork and establish more efficient workflows as multiple users or applications can work simultaneously on the same datasets. This should ensure consistent and synchronized efforts [31]. Moreover, data sharing may support personalized shopping experiences as retailers can gain a deeper understanding of their customers' profiles, behaviors, and expectations. As a result, they may recommend relevant products, and offer tailored promotions, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty [5]. Besides, it is hoped that sharing data across the retail value chain, including merchandising, supply chain, e-commerce, and physical stores, allows for better decision-making in two ways: first, it provides insights into customer behavior, preferences, and trends, enabling retailers to make informed choices about products and promotions [6]. Second, it may support strengthening fair and ecologically valuable practices through enhanced transparency along the supply chain. Yet, these benefits can only be realized through responsible and secure data sharing practices that prioritize user privacy and data protection.

In the European energy sector, data sharing fosters innovation by granting access to more data for companies and start-ups, leading to new products and services and advancing renewable energy, efficiency, and grid management. This fosters a sustainable energy system. It promotes collaboration among stakeholders, aiding the green transition. Sharing data on consumption patterns and renewable energy aids in identifying strategies to reduce emissions. Additionally, data sharing enhances affordability and accessibility, with energy companies offering personalized saving recommendations. Energy communities exemplify data-dependent sharing systems, reshaping the role of traditional energy players. Thus, data sharing here enables and pushes a fundamental transition of the energy sector [9]. Overall, data sharing in the European energy sector sets out to drive innovation for supporting the green transition, and potentially to enhance energy affordability and accessibility for individuals and communities.

In the European telecom sector, benefits of data sharing relate to accelerated innovation and improved customer experience as well as beyond. By sharing data, telecom companies can gain insights into customer behavior, preferences, and needs, which allows to enhance customer service, personalize offerings, and provide a better overall experience for users [7]. Moreover, sharing data within the telecom sector can foster collaboration and innovation as telecom companies can leverage shared data to develop new products, services, and solutions that meet the evolving needs of users. This can lead to technological advancements, improved connectivity, and better communication options. Moreover, data sharing may enhance performance and efficiency of telecommunication infrastructure. By analyzing data on network traffic, usage patterns, and performance metrics, operators can identify areas that require improvements, reduce congestion, and ensure better connectivity for users.

In addition, data sharing may hold environmental and safety benefits. For example, it may contribute to reducing the carbon footprint and energy consumption in the telecom sector. By analyzing data on traffic patterns, telecom companies can optimize routing and reduce the time spent in traffic, resulting in lower emissions. Additionally, data sharing can help optimize the energy efficiency of buildings and cars, leading to reduced energy consumption. Yet, the environmental impact of increasing digitalization remains under research. Regarding public safety, data sharing enables telecom operators to collaborate with authorities and emergency services during critical situations. By sharing data on network performance, coverage, and user locations, telecom operators can support efficient emergency response, ensure public safety, and enable faster communication during emergencies.

As these examples show, hopes for (indirect) business opportunities through data sharing run high with additional societal and ecological benefits on the side. DATAMITE explores the perspective of ‘benefits beyond monetization’ even further. Ongoing calls for sustainability and social responsibility invite businesses to acknowledge that they are not isolated from society. Rather, they are deeply socially embedded and intricately woven into society, thus, they ground discourses on business ethics, their responsibilities, and future working environments in tangible reality. Depending on their role, structure and tasks, businesses need to consider societal benefits, e.g. when responsible for supply security or providing general infrastructure. Yet, paying dues to this social embedding may hold benefits beyond monetization for other businesses as well, irrespective whether it is big companies and small businesses, regarding reputation.

These benefits, however, are sector-specific and hence prioritized differently according to the respective business field. To identify and specify potential impacts and benefits for each of its sectors (energy, telecommunication, agriculture, urban services, meteorological forecasting), the project DATAMITE differentiated within a workshop impacts of data sharing in six dimensions: societal, macro-economic, customer-oriented, scientific, security and ecological impacts (Figure 1). Some dimensions focus on the mechanisms of indirect data monetization, i.e. enhancing existing products, services, or operations, in short, providing added value; this appeared true for consumer-oriented, macro-economic, scientific and security, and partly ecological impacts. Others, however, provide opportunities to strengthen businesses’ reputation, particularly in the light of sustainability and inclusion (ecological and social impacts). Concerning market equality, data sharing has even been contemplated to address and rectify market imbalances, which would hold advantages especially for smaller businesses. While preliminary, these results indicate that considering impacts and benefits beyond monetization will indeed support business in their daily work.

Thus, the diverse social implications bring chances for sustainability and equity by fostering innovation, improving services, and promoting social justice. An increased data availability might support more informed political decisions, but caution is urged to critically evaluate potential implications. Ecological impacts can benefit by stressing circular economy, by emphasizing efficient energy use

Fig. 1. Impact beyond monetization [12]

and green energy generation while environmental benefits could i.e. include the optimization of product logistics or digital product passports. The most obvious implication is the benefit for interdisciplinary collaboration, adherence to FAIR principles, and the potential for innovative services. Supply chains as well as consumers benefit from the increased transparency is highlighted, particularly in supply chains like food production. On a macroeconomic level benefit extend to better energy budget control and economic growth opportunities. Data sharing and open data can lead to sustainable economic decisions and can improve private-public sector cooperation, addressing social problems along supply chains.

3.2 Challenges

Non-monetary impacts of personal data monetization. Both direct and indirect monetization of personal data as data products or otherwise carry special business, legal, technological, and ethical requirements, and consequences.

Business considerations Trust, reputation, and public relations. "For companies, being trusted as a brand is a critical requirement. If your customers do not trust you, they will vote with their feet and take their business elsewhere. (Naturally, this does not apply to companies with monopolistic market positions such as highlighted by the example above of Google.) Encouraging brand loyalty – a manifestation of customer trust – is therefore a key strategic goal for both consumer and B2B companies. The flip side of this goal is to avoid the kind of damage to one's brand that adversely affects customer loyalty. A visible breach

of trust – being seen as untrustworthy – is one of the most effective ways to destroy established brand loyalty." [19]

Organizational Typical obstacles for companies and organisations to participate in data exchange include [33]:

- Lack of agreement on new roles and their task descriptions
- Insufficient data quality
- Concerns about losing control of their valuable data and trade secrets if they share it with others
- Concerns about unintentionally undermining data protection rules
- Difficulties in demonstrating the benefits of data sharing; lack of definition of success and value of data ecosystems including a sustainable business model for data monetization

Individuals are also demanding fairness, transparency and better control over the use of their personal data. There is a great need to improve trust in data and AI and at the same time create trust between the parties involved. A freely downloadable rulebook has been developed [28] to provide a framework and guideline to cover most of these aspects, but their applicability needs to be adjusted to the boundary conditions of every company context.

When adapting a rulebook to usage we have very often found, that organizations have not yet achieved the sufficient maturity of their data strategy for sharing to actually apply the rulebook for data monetization. A data monetization maturity model is needed to assess the precondition of every organization before application and systematically guide the organization to realize and overcome their deficits.

Also, once such rules are agreed upon, their control and enforcement with big data volumes is problematic. An automation needs to be found to translate the contracts into actual code above the data connectors as manual control is then prohibitive.

Technological Anonymization. Companies who want to monetize personal data will often seek to anonymize it first in order not to fall into the scope of GDPR requirements. However, currently available technological methods for anonymization are either not sufficient to guarantee absolute anonymity of the people concerned or so demanding as to be impractical for most companies [8, 26]. When personal data is not anonymized and therefore remains within the scope of the GDPR (even after, e.g., pseudonymization), its monetization will usually require cybersecurity measures as with any confidential data.

Data usage Data exploitation, particularly in industries working with sensitive information, as is the health sector, for example, is constrained by strict laws. Data monetisation is sometimes also hindered by rules and regulations preventing companies from using their data and operating in any other business venture

except the one in which they currently operate. Furthermore, the access or self of personal data perse could sometimes be considered ethically or even legally questionable in some industry sectors. Since data providers are in no control concerning the final use of the data being sold, which could result in illegal or unethical data usage, measures for establishing mechanisms to discover the final use of data must be taken by providers. What is more, the recognition of potential risks may guide companies in setting up relevant contracts, thereby taking stringent governance actions.

Security and privacy Respect for the right to privacy of data subjects is further enhanced through the implementation of a Data Security Policy by data administrators and processors. Both technical and organisational measures should be installed to guarantee compliance with the requirements set forth in the GDPR. Systems implementing "data protection by design" ought to have quantitative and/or qualitative metrics to prove that dedicated measures are put in place to ensure continuous oversight and mitigation of potential data protection risks.

Standardisation The lack of general guidelines and standards for data storage, processing, and trading, globally, is yet another regulatory challenge. The lack of common standards thus leads to interoperable solutions, thereby hindering data exchange and integration, but also increasing the risk of vendor lock-in.

Legal The spectrum of legal and regulatory issues to be considered when data monetisation is the goal, is wide. Lack of legal compliance may thus not only be against established legal requirements perse, but it may also lead to multiple problems such as damaged reputation of a company. The rapidly evolving legal framework and oftentimes, the ambiguity of provisions, as is the case with certain aspects of GDPR, has not made it any easier for companies and organisations striving to achieve compliance when personal or highly sensitive data is involved. As the legal and regulatory framework evolves, so do the challenges emerge, but the most prominent thus far may be summarised to: data usage, data ownership, liability, cross-border data flows and global trade, and standardization [20].

Ownership and Legal Liability It may be argued that data ownership is rather complicated due to the non-rivalrous nature of data, thereby giving rise to conflicts with regard to data sharing. A major problem in this regard, is the difficulty in recognising who is the owner of the data, as the latter flows through long and complicated value networks, and thus, who is to be held liable in case of faulty data and analysis leading to negative consequences.

With due regard to the above, and the full consideration of any major legal liability challenges that may be posed by data monetisation, companies must be vigilant in addressing the usage of employees, but also any other third-party's data in their offerings [20].

Cross-Border Data Trade It may be the case that data monetization entails more than one jurisdiction, as is the scenario when data collected in one jurisdiction is being transferred to parties in another. Due to the yet lacking comprehensive regulatory framework on data sharing and monetization on global scale, multiple jurisdictional problems are on the raise. Despite the unified regulatory framework concerning data security in personal privacy in the EU, the US, for example, differs in that different laws are applicable in different states and across different industries.

Ethics & Trust Data, in that regard, involves additional ethical perplexities when it comes to monetisation of the available resources at a said organisation. While safeguarding the right to privacy is the leading concern, context-driven mitigation measures could be necessary, nevertheless, in cases of automated administration of data, data analytics and/or handling of sensitive data, etc.

Ethical data handling should be defined, in the first place, as a broader framework than lawful data processing, which ensures appropriate safeguards for fundamental rights and fairness throughout the administration. While some mitigation measures might fulfill the requirements to be legally compliant, risks of discrimination, stigmatisation or lack of transparency, leading to breaches of the right to privacy might still occur. To properly address prospective negative impact on individuals' rights and dignity, data administrators should in many cases carry out data protection impact assessment in accordance with Art. 35 GDPR. Such is needed in all cases of the so called "high-risk" data processing which may include among others processing of sensitive data, big-data analytics, data mining, usage of automated tools, profiling and/or evaluation and other hypotheses in which the data subject may have a limited information and/or control over their personal data.

Transparency and accountability, in the second place, are key prerequisites to any data-driven solution. The EU Charter of fundamental rights requires fairness in data processing, which is further developed by the principles set forth in Art. 5 GDPR. Companies and individuals who would like to monetise their data would need to ensure that personal data are preferably anonymised, or if not feasible – that data subjects are thoroughly informed of how their data would be used and what implications this entails to their privacy, and have provided their explicit consent, accordingly.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, data monetization in Europe offers significant opportunities for revenue generation, enhanced decision-making, and innovation. However, challenges such as regulatory compliance and organizational barriers hinder its realization. The DATAMITE research project addresses these hurdles by providing a comprehensive framework to streamline the monetization process. Through modules focusing on data governance, quality assurance, and security, DATAMITE empowers users to maximize the value of their data assets. By fostering trust,

collaboration, and participation in data ecosystems, DATAMITE accelerates the growth and competitiveness of European industries in the digital economy.

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